

**INVESTIGATION INTO MECHANICS OF COMPRESSION BEHAVIOUR
OF TEMIDIRE, ILUBIRIN, GBELEJULODA, AND IRELEJARE TAR
SAND, ONDO STATE**

BY

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**A THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF MINING ENGINEERING,
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FEBRUARY, 2022

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis titled “Investigation into Mechanics of Compression Behaviour of Temidire, Ilubirin, Gbelejuloda, and Irelejare Tar Sand, Ondo State” was written by me and is a correct record of my research work. It has not been presented in any previous application for any degree of this or any other University, only that part of the results from this work has been presented in different international conferences and also sent for journal publication. All citations and sources of information are clearly acknowledged by means of references.

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this thesis entitled “Investigation into Mechanics of Compression Behaviour of Temidire, Ilubirin, Gbelejuloda, and Irelejare Tar Sand, Ondo State” is the outcome of the research carried out by Olamijulo, Oluwapelumi Emmanuel (MNE/11/5414) in the Department of Mining Engineering, The Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, in Partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of Master of Engineering (M.Eng) Degree in Mining Engineering.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this project work to Almighty God that gave me the life, wisdom and strength to do the work. His name be praised.

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the compression behaviour of the Temidire, Ilubirin, Gbelejuloda and Irelejare Tar sands in Ondo State through a series of oedometer test on the samples in the intact and reconstituted states. Understanding engineering behaviour of material is imperative to safe mine design, this knowledge is scarce for Ondo state Tar sands. Representative samples were collected from four different locations at various depths through block sampling. The samples were investigated, by carrying out classification and index test, microstructure and geochemistry were studied using SEM equipped with EDS. The mineralogy was investigated using XRD and uniaxial compressive strength test was carried out. Sand fraction has a great influence on the behaviour of the tar sand, because for all location considered the lowest was 80.5% and highest was 95.5%, with very low fines for all the locations. The SEM result confirmed the significant disturbance affecting the intact samples, showing pores located between dense inter clusters, and the fabric are homogenous. The mineralogy is dominated by quartz for all the samples and other minerals. The samples converged to unique intrinsic normal compression lines indicating no significant transitional mode of behaviour with respect to depth. The intrinsic compressibility of the tar sand was low due to high sand fraction. The effects of structure, which is the degree of enhanced resistance of the natural sample in compression, using normalization no effect of structure was found for GB samples due to low initial void ratio, but for others effect of structure were positive and small. Using stress sensitivities approach effects of structure were positive for all the samples. For the post yield behaviour, at the highest stresses reached in the tests, the samples have been completely destructured. From the uniaxial compressive strength test, the values ranges from 28.9 kPa to 52.1 kPa and the UCS value increases with depth.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

For more than eight decades, severe studies have been carried out on the Nigeria Tar sand deposit. The geological survey team from the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University), Ile-Ife led by Professor O. S. Adegoke, carried out research on this material in the early 80's (Adedimila, 1980). Previous findings on this material were majorly based on their geographical, geological and geochemical facts (e.g., Ekweozor and Nwachukwu, 1989; Adegoke *et al.*, 1980; Adegoke 1980; Adebisi *et al.*, 2005, 2007). The mineralogy, physical characteristics and also the geotechnical properties of this material has also been studied (e.g., Akinmosin *et al.*, 2013; and Ola, 1991). Tar sand can also be referred to as oil sand or bituminous sand (most appropriately should called bituminous sand), can be used as a construction material for flexible pavement construction, and the bitumen extracted from it, is used as a waterproof material for road surfacing and as a potential raw material for the polymer and petrochemical industries for the production of resins, plastics and fibres (Ola, 1991).

Tar sand is an example of carbon-rich sedimentary rock like coal and oil shale. All mineral rocks containing solid organic matter in form of kerogen are usually referred to as carbon-rich sedimentary rocks. This organic matter can be converted by pyrolysis into synthetic fuel (Rajaa *et al.*, 2018). Bituminous sands are found in several countries around the world, including the former Soviet Union, Venezuela, Canada, Cuba, Indonesia, Brazil, Jordan,

Madagascar, Trinidad, Colombia, Albania, Rumania, Spain, Portugal, Argentina, and Nigeria. The United States contains scattered deposits of oil sands, mainly in Utah, Kentucky, Kansas, Missouri, California, and New Mexico (Francis, 2016). Significant reserves of heavy oil (bitumen) are located in Nigeria, are usually found in sand deposits, which are mainly located in south west region, majorly from Ondo state and Ogun state (Adedimila, 2000).

Due to the fact that effort is been made progressively in developing improved technology for recovery of bitumen from tar sands, it is logical to assume that as the world's supply of light and heavy oil is depleted, production of synthetic oil from the bitumen resources in tar sands will accelerate (Francis, 2016). As most of the known deposits of tar sands were discovered by accident, and few by geological survey, there is reason to believe that a more detail worldwide exploration program can lead more discoveries of this material. And the need to access and mine this mineral resource has made it imperative to investigate it's engineering behaviour.

Many problems confronting the engineers in the field of soil and rock engineering are geologically, microstructural and mineralogical related. This implies the need for further investigations on the microstructural and mineralogy composition of materials and their contributions to the properties these materials that can influence their behaviour and also acquire knowledge on the compression behaviour. Though extensive geological studies had been conducted on the natural occurring tar sand, but adequate information about the engineering behaviour of Ondo state Tar sand is scare. This research is focused on characterization of tar sand base on its compression behaviour in an incremental oedometer test, in addition to this, classification and index test were carried out, mineralogy and

microstructure were investigated, strength behaviour were investigated also, so as to be able to elucidate their engineering behaviour based on these parameters.

1.2 Problem Statement

Previous findings on Ondo State Tar sand were mainly on geographical, geological and geochemical characteristics, knowledge about their detailed engineering behaviour is inadequate, especially their compression behaviour. There are two different forms of loading system viz, compression and shearing. It is very important to understand the compression behaviour of materials because it is the simplest form of loading that materials can undergo after formation or deposition as well as post depositional processes. Predicting the failure around geotechnical structures under loading is of great important in carrying out engineering design and analysis, (Okewale 2019, 2020). This research was able to characterized Ondo state Tar sand for all the selected locations based on their compression behavior, through their physical, mechanical properties, microstructural, geochemical, mineralogical characteristics and one-dimensional test of the samples in their reconstituted and natural states was carried out, using conventional front loading oedometer.

1.3 Aim of the Research

The aim of the research is to investigate the mechanics of compression behaviour of Ondo State Tar sand

1.4 Objectives of the Research

The specific objectives of the research are to:

- a) determine physical and index properties of tar sand;
- b) investigate mineralogy, microstructure and determine the geochemical of the tar sand;
- c) estimate compressibility from oedometer tests;

- d) determine effects of geological structure; and,
- e) investigate the strength property of tar sand from uniaxial compressive strength test.

1.5 Justification of the Research

High content of bitumen in the tar sand composition makes the naturally occurring sands of low load-bearing materials for the hauling trucks, shovels and some other mining and construction equipment. In situ, the tar sand deposits are predominantly quartz sand with little percentage of clay and water, with bitumen filling up the pore spaces within the sand grains (Joseph and Tutumuler, 2012). Geotechnical, geochemical and geomechanical characteristics, such as lithology, mineralogy, microstructural, grain size distribution, groundwater conditions and some others varies widely between different deposits, and even within a given deposit with respect to location and their depth. Only few studies have been carried out on the microstructure and mineralogy of Nigeria tar sand. The studies have not been able to give extensive engineering behaviour and how microstructure and mineralogy of this material influence the compression behaviour. This necessitates the need to investigate the compression behaviour of this material.

1.6 Scope of the Research

This research includes collection of samples from four different locations in two local government areas in Ondo state. Samples were collected along a vertical profile in all locations in block form (JGS, 1995). Though, materials were collected at shallow depth, because the highest depth reached was 2 m, this was due to unavailability of standard machinery to recovery the materials at deeper depth. Index properties, mechanical properties, mineralogical analysis, chemical and microstructural analyses were conducted and were related to their compression behaviour.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 TAR SAND

Tar sand is a potential resource in Nigeria yet to be exploited since the year of discovery. However, continuous researches have been carried out on this material till this present time, hoping to commence full exploitation of this tar sand just like that of Athabasca oil sand in Canada. The occurrence of these deposits has been known since early last century. However, intense investigations commenced from mid 70's till now. The geology of these deposits, oil saturation and reserve estimates as well as textural characteristics of the associated sands have been described (e.g, Adegoke et al., 1981; Enu, 1985). The origin of the bituminous sand has also been studied (e.g, Adegoke *et al.*, 1981; Ademodi *et al.*, 1987; Enu, 1985). Other relevant studies on the deposit include works done by Ako *et al.*, (1983); Ekweozor and Nwachukwu, (1989); and Enu, (1985). All these studies have been able to highlight relevant aspects of the geochemical and sedimentological characteristics of the deposit.

Investigations on the Nigeria oil sands (tar sands) with respect to their mechanical behaviour, compression behaviour, stress-strain behaviour, mineralogical and microstructural characteristics and some other engineering properties have not been thoroughly studied. Few researches have been carried out on tar sand based on their physico-mechanical properties, geotechnical characteristics, and determination of reservoir characteristics (such as grain size parameters) in order to assist with future production procedures (e.g., Ola, 1991; Adewale *et al.*, 2013). Ola, (1991) investigated the geotechnical properties and behaviour of the Nigeria tar sand. He found that the Nigeria tar sand behaved as a soft sandstone. The compacted tar sand behaved like an over consolidated soil. Investigation on the physical and chemical

characterization of tar sands observed at Imeri in Ogun State, south-western, gave some insight into the physical properties (Akinyemi, 2013). Akinmosin et al., (2008) mainly emphasize on the particle size distribution and mineralogy of forty-four samples of tar sand from the Afowo formation.

2.2 Nigerian Bituminous Sand

Nigeria has an appreciable large deposit of natural bituminous sand (popularly called the Tar sand) which is sometimes refer to as oil sand or oil impregnated sand. The Nigerian tar sand deposits can be found within the confine of the eastern margin of Dahomey basin which lies within a deposit belt cutting across three major states which include: Ogun, Ondo, Edo states in the South-western and South-southern Nigeria respectively. Tar sand is composed mainly of heavy oil and clays that are rich in mineral and waters. This heavy oil content of tar sand is commonly called bitumen. In the raw state tar sand is a strictly black viscous substance. The total reserve of heavy oil is estimated to exceed 30 billion barrel (Adegoke, 1980). Tar sands is wide spread in the South-western part of Nigeria in minable, economical quantity. Significant works have been carried out by various personnel on the geology, origin, and occurrence of Tar sand in Nigeria. The Dahomey basin is a coastal sedimentary basin filled with over 2500 m length of cretaceous and younger sediments uncomfortable overlying the block faulted basement complex rocks. The basin's sedimentary fill was subdivided into three intervals namely, sand and sandstones at the base, alternating sands and shale and, Upper shales which correspond to the three formations of Ise, Afowo and Araromi respectively.

2.3 Ondo State Bituminous Sand

The naturally occurring bituminous materials of the Ondo State deposits are found in two basic forms on site (Adegoke, 1980; Ako *et al.*, 1980) namely, bitumen seepages from wells

which yield plain bitumen, i.e bitumen not noticeably associated with sand. This is soft at ordinary temperature and low viscosity bitumen e.g., the Agbabu and Ilubirin deposits, seepages and outcrops of bitumen-impregnated sands from which bitumen can be extracted by steam injection and in situ combustion methods, which is generally referred to as 'tar sands' but should more appropriately be called bituminous sands' since tar cannot occur in nature e.g., Gbelejuloda deposits. Lately, much attention have been drawn to the need of extracted the bitumen deposits of Ondo state in Nigeria. Even though much of their efforts (especially the earlier attempts) have been of a fragmentary manner; the reliability of information on the materials has been improving especially in recent years resulting in desirable growth of useful information on the deposits. Some of the findings have been documented in papers published in reputable scientific and technical journals as well as published reports which remain largely obscure.

2.4 Index and Physical Properties

Index properties of material enable us to understand the engineering behaviour of materials and their classifications. They involve soil grain properties (grain size, shape, and distribution) and soil aggregate properties. Few researches have been able to establish the index and physical properties of Nigerian tar sand (e.g., grain size, grain shapes, water content, clay content, porosity, liquid limit, plastic limit, plasticity index, linear shrinkage, optimum water content (OMC), maximum dry density (MDD), and specific gravity). According to Akinbinu (2003) and Afeni (2003) the grain sizes of Ondo State tar bearing sands vary from fine to coarse-grained. The clay content range between 2% to 7% with average of 5%, water content is about 1-5%. Afeni (2003) stated that the grain shapes of the tar sand observed are round, the grains show a wide variation and ranged from sub angular

to sub rounded. It was however observed that the fine grains are more angular than the coarse grains. The inter granular voids are occupied by oil, water and air. The porosity of the tar sands varies from one sample to another because of the variability of pore spaces in the sediments. The particle size distribution (PSD) curve for the mixture of Ilubirin samples by Ola (1991) shows that the mixture is well-graded, coarse to medium-fine silty sand. According to AASTHO method of soil classification it is an A-2-4, only 5% of this mixture is of clay size, which corresponds to the clay content range of 2-7% for Nigerian tar sands, and is reasonably lower than the average for Athabasca, Canada (10-25%) (Enu, 1985). The physical properties of the tar sand sample from Ilubirin was investigated by Ola (1991), specific gravity, bulk density, moisture content values of the Ilubirin samples was established in the work. The Atterberg limits were determined after extracting the bitumen from the "tar" sand. In addition, the range of specific gravity obtained by Adedimila (1987) was within 2.3-2.6 which also agrees with the specific gravity result (2.58) obtained by Ola (1991).

2.5 Atterberg Limits

In an endeavour to determine the effect of the clay fraction on the engineering properties of soil, an analysis has been made of the results of the Atterberg plasticity tests which are carried out as routine classification tests. These comprise of the liquid limit, the plastic limit and the shrinkage limit. These limits were created by Albert Atterberg a Swedish chemist, which were later refined by Arthur Casagrande (Casagrande and Fadum 1940).

2.5.1 Liquid Limit

The liquid limit is the moisture content at which a soil passes from a plastic to liquid state. The liquid limit depends on the fine particles present. The liquid limit of a mixture of clay and sand decreases as the percent clay in the mixture decreases but the liquid limit per unit

weight of the clay remains essentially constant, high liquid limits indicate soils of clay content and low load carrying capacity (Omomomi, 2020).

2.5.2 Plastic Limit

The plastic limit of soils is the moisture content at which a soil changes from a semi-solid to a plastic state. This condition is said to prevail when the soil contains just enough moisture that it can be rolled into 3 mm diameter threads without breaking (Tazen et al., 2016). The plastic limit is governed by clay content. Some silt and sandy soils that cannot be rolled into 3 mm threads at any moisture content have no plastic limit and are termed non-plastic (Omomomi 2020).

2.5.3 Shrinkage Limit

The shrinkage limit of a soil is defined as the point which no further volume decrease occurs on drying. The water content at which this occurs is called the shrinkage limit. The shrinkage limit of soils depends on their clay content, high swelling clays containing the mineral montmorillonite can absorb large amounts of water and hence shrink considerably on drying (Omomomi, 2020). The shrinkage limit is primarily a function of soil plasticity, it is expected to decrease with an increase in liquid limit and plasticity (Omomomi, 2020).

2.6 Microstructural and Chemical Analysis

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is a test process that scans a sample with an electron beam to produce a magnified image for analysis. Electron microscopy is performed at high magnifications, generates high-resolution images and precisely measures very small features and objects. The signals generated during SEM analysis produce a two-dimensional image and reveal information about the sample, including external morphology (texture), chemical composition, when used with the EDS feature, and orientation of materials making up the

sample. These samples will be studied under dry condition. Doan (2011), Doan *et al.*, (2012), Pierre *et al.*, (2013) and Pierre *et al.*, (2012) had some details about the microstructure of oil sands (Canadian oil sands), in which the image shows dense clusters composed of highly angular grains (light gray) and fluids (gray). Microstructural study of this material is very scarce unlike some other materials, such as lateritic soils, clay, talc, shale and others (e.g., Chow *et al.* 2018; Ng *et al.* 2019; Okewale and Grobber 2020b, 2020c; Okewale and Coop 2017, Okewale 2021).

2.7 Mineralogical Analysis

X-ray diffractometer consist of three basic elements, an X-ray tube, a sample holder, and an X-ray detector. Quartz is the dominant mineral of the tar sand and it constitutes over 90% of the entire assemblage of the mineral grains, feldspar, mica and clay occur in minor amounts (Afeni, 2013). XRD analysis carried out on athabasca oil sand showed that the sample was composed of close to 99 % of quartz (Pierre, *et al.*; 2013). Clay mineral studied on Agbabu tar sand sequence revealed that clays mainly composed of kaolinite, illite, smectite, and mixed layers in small amounts. The clay content in the tar-impregnated sand is lower (2-7%) than that, present in the lower sands devoid of tar (7-20%) (Afeni, 2013), but this was limited to Agbabu tar sand only, effort has not been made to look at other locations that host this material, so has to be able to establish the variation of clay mineral in this material with respect to different locations. Some other findings have been done on the investigation of the mineral composition of tar sands apart from clay minerals (e.g., Adebisi *et al.*, 2008; Akinmosin *et al.*, 2008). But none of this study have been able to establish relationship of the mineralogy and strength of this material, which is a vital parameter in describing their engineering behaviour, because different mineral varies in hardness.

2.8 Consolidation

The consolidation properties of soils indicate the settlement of structures. The oedometer step-loading consolidation test is one of the most widely used tests in the soil mechanics laboratory. It was introduced by Terzaghi as an experimental support for his one-dimensional consolidation theory (Terzaghi, 1943). The original consolidation theory was developed by Karl Terzaghi, and this theory is still valid and is used for almost all consolidation problems in geotechnical engineering. Terzaghi work was the first starting place of all studies of consolidation as well as other subjects to the deformation porous media with flowing fluid through the medium (Jeerevipoolvarn, 2005). According to Persio *et al.*, (2017), the main target of the consolidation test is to acquire knowledge about the consolidation characteristics of a soil from the measured settlement time curve. From this consolidation theory, those characteristics are been expressed by both the coefficient of soil consolidation c_v and the total consolidation settlement δ_{100} (Taylor, 1948). The safety, reliability, and overall stiffness of structures are affected by heterogeneity and, by extension, the differential settlements of the soil (Frantziskonisa and Breyssi, 2013). This is evident in the coastal areas of different countries, just like some coastal areas in India where foundations of erected structures settled at a rate from 10 to 100cm/s. This alarming settlement rate was traced to several reasons such as consolidation, creep failure due to excessive loading, volume reduction in soil due to shrinkage, and settlement due to reduction in water content. Shanyoug *et al.*, (2009) found that as the fraction of fines in weathered granite increases, the permeability decreases due to a reduction in void ratio. However, they reported that the coefficient of consolidation increases with higher fines content. With increasing clay-size fraction, the soil becomes more plastic, and its swelling and shrinkage potential increases and so does its compressibility

(Dimitova and Yanful, 2012). Therefore, induced settlement of soil is a function of the increase in pore water pressure caused by the loading, the reduction in pressure overtime, and permeability of the in situ soils (Bello *et al.*, 2019). To avoid settlement, routinely one-dimensional consolidation test is usually carried out to determine the settlement parameters of soils, namely compression index (C_c), consolidation coefficient of volume compressibility (M_v), and swelling index (C_s).

2.9 Compressibility

The decrease in volume per unit increase of pressure is defined as the compressibility of soil. A measure of the rate at which consolidation proceeds is given by the co-efficient of consolidation of the soil (Dimitova and Yanful, 2012). Adepoju *et al.*, (2018) noted that compressibility of soils is a function of reduced initial volume of void and increased hydraulic conductivity of soils. In order to avoid the overwhelming experimental time and cost involved in determining the complex but important one-dimensional consolidation test on soils, researchers have established some correlations between coefficient of consolidation and varying plasticity properties of clayey soils.

Watabe *et al.*, (2011) found that the compression index increases linearly as the amount of clay increases. According to Okewale (2020) when investigating the compressibility and effects of structure of clay in an increasing loading oedometer test, the intrinsic behavior of soils was consistent with fines content, plasticity and clay minerals, and it was observed that the finer and better-graded soil with higher fines content, plasticity and clay minerals content have higher compressibility.

It has been widely recognized that the compressibility of natural soils is clearly different from that of reconstituted soils owing to the soil structure effect (e.g., Burland, 1990; Cotecchia and Chandler, 2000; Okewale and Coop, 2017, 2018a, 2020; Okewale and Grobler

2020a, 2020b, 2021). Otoko (2015) studied the dependence of shear strength and compressibility on clay content of some tropical laterite soils and established that compressibility has a direct proportionality with clay content. From the above considerations, clayey soils generally possess low void ratio, and, under saturated condition and increased pore water pressure caused by loading, they settle.

Elaborate understanding of compression behavior of materials is essential particularly in deformation calculations and understanding of effect of structure. This is why this research will be systematically investigating the compressibility of Ondo state tar sand. This study is new for this particular material.

2.10 Intrinsic Behaviour

The compression behaviour of reconstituted soil is termed intrinsic behaviour. This behaviour results solely from the constituent particles of the soil. This is very essential because intrinsic compressibility parameters gotten from one-dimensional compression curve of reconstituted samples are required for engineering design (Okewale 2020a, 2020b, 2021). Intrinsic properties of material are important in giving a detail engineering characteristic of any material, and knowledge about the intrinsic properties is incomplete without proper findings into their compression behavior, in understanding geological structures, compression test often establish the effect of this structure in engineering application. Void index I_v and I_{vH} proposed by Burland (1990) and Horpibulsuk et al. (2011) was introduced respectively to evaluate their intrinsic compressibility. From the findings of their work, it was concluded that I_v was more suitable for depicting the compression behaviour of pure clays than I_{vH} , whereas, for the compressibility of sand-clay mixture, the normalized compression line by using I_v was obviously different from that of pure clays and

traditional soils due to the presence of sand particles. Therefore, a four-phase analysis framework of sand-clay mixture was introduced to unify the intrinsic compression behavior of soils with and without sands. The state of reconstituted soils does not change with disturbance, and their properties refer to the basic or inherent properties of the soil, which Burland (1990) defined as intrinsic. The compression curve of the natural soil in comparison to the location of the normal compression line of the reconstituted material or the intrinsic compression line (ICL) can then be used as a measure of the influence of the structure on the compression behaviour.

2.11 Effect of Structure

The term structure refers to a combination of bonding (an interparticle forces which are not purely frictional) and fabric (an arrangement of particles) (Leroueil and Vaughan 1990; Cotecchia and Chandler 2000; Yin *et al.*, 2011; Zeng *et al.*, 2016; Okewale and Grobber, 2021).

The fabric includes inhomogeneities, layering, any distinct distribution or orientation of the soil particles and fissures. The structure of clay is a physicochemical equilibrium between the soil as a result of depositional and post depositional processes. The characteristics of a soil structure are the consequences of the processes that the soil has undergone, and therefore any soil in any state, either intact or reconstituted, can be considered to have a structure (Gasparre and Coop, 2008). According Gasparre and Coop (2008) in a studied undertaken on quantification of the effects of structure on the compression of a stiff clay, the term structure is used for clays in there intact state, for which the structure depends on the geological history of the soil, Burland (1990) further explained that a fully destructured state is defined as the state of a clay that has been reconstituted at a mater content equal to or

greater than the liquid limit without air or oven drying and consolidated under one-dimensional conditions.

Some studies have presented the effects of structure of clay and some other materials, and their compression behaviour. For example, Wang and Yan (2006) studied two common saprolites from Hong Kong but only from one location and quite narrow depth ranges. Their study revealed that intact samples exhibited a yield stress that was not abrupt but rather gradual in isotropic loading which they concluded was the result of the presence of bonding, and that effect of structure is positive. Rocchi and Coop (2015) studied extensively the effects of weathering on the physical and mechanical behaviour of granitic saprolites also from Hong Kong along a profile up to a depth of 40m, but again only from one location. They found that as the weathering increased (or depth reduced) there were clear changes to the mineralogy that accompanied a grading that became finer and better graded, while the in-situ specific volume increased and the effects of structure reduced. Okewale (2020) investigated the compressibility and the effects of structure of tropical clay in incremental oedometer loading, from his findings, the compression paths of the natural soils reach a state outside their respective intrinsic normal compression line. The effects of structure applying normalization to compare the behaviour of the natural and reconstituted samples show small to medium effects of structure in compression. The effects of structure using sensitivity analyses show positive but small effects of structure. Within the scatter of the data, the two methods applied shows positive the effects of structure of this tropical clay for both locations studied. Similar result was reported about shale and talc by Okewale and Grobber, (2020c), (2021). But for tar sands this has not been established before now.

2.12 Mechanical Behaviour

One of the important parameters to describe the mechanical behaviour of material is the strength characterization, which is also an essential parameter in engineering designs.

2.12.1 Uniaxial Compressive Strength

Compressive strength is the capacity of a material to withstand axially directed compressive forces (Balasubramanian, 2017). The most common measure of compressive strength is the uniaxial compressive strength also known as unconfined compressive strength. The summary of strength properties of Nigerian tar sand (Ilubrin deposit) was given in table 11 (Ola, 1991), the compressive strength of the in situ sample was given to be 450kN/m^2 , tending to the strength of a very weak, fractured or soft sandstone.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

The materials used in this research were tar sands. They were collected from four different locations. The samples were collected from Irele and Odigbo local government area of Ondo state, the specific locations were Irelejare, Gbelejuloda, Temidire and Ilubirin as shown in figure 3.1. The coordinates of the sample locations are presented in table 3.1, the method of sampling (block method) (JGS, 1995) were shown in plate 3.1a and b. The tar sands were excavated at different depth, the maximum depth reached was 2.0m below ground level as shown in the table 3.2 below. Tar sands obtained were investigated at different depth, this helps in knowing the variability and trend of properties along a profile (Okewale, 2020a, 2020b.). The samples were careful trimmed, and retrieved in block form from the bottom at each depth with the use cutlass and hand-held saw (JGS, 1995), and were immediately kept in a white nylon than packed in another black sacks so as to retain the in-situ water content, after which the samples were transported to the Engineering Geology Laboratory, of the Geology Department of the Federal University of Technology, Akure for laboratory tests. The details of the samples are given in the table below, for simplicity acronyms were used for the samples.

Figure 3.1 Geological Map of the Ondo Study Showing the Study Areas

Table 3.1 Details of Sample Locations

S/N	SAMPLE LOCATION	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE
1	Temidare	4° 49' 49.458" E	6° 36' 55.82412" N
2	Ilubirin	4° 49' 44.4658" E	6° 43' 52.73184" N
3	Gbelejuloda	4° 53' 28.79628" E	6° 39' 16.35372" N
4	Irelejare	4° 48' 77.9677" E	6° 39' 20.07072" N

Table 3.2 Details of Sample Characteristics

Sample Location	Acronym	Depth (m)
Irelejare	RJ 1	0.75
	RJ 2	1.45
	RJ 3	2.0
Gbelejuloda	GB1	0.5
	GB2	0.9
	GB3	1.3
Temidire	TM1	0.4
	TM2	0.8
	TM3	1.5
Ilubirin	LU1	0.3
	LU2	0.6
	LU3	1.1

Plate 3.1 Sample Collection by Block Sampling Method

3.2 Methods

The laboratory test carried out on the Tar sands was to determine the following properties, index properties, physical and mechanical properties, mineralogy, microstructure, and chemical composition. Microstructural analysis was carried out on the samples to characterize the samples' by using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analyzer and mineralogy was investigated using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). Results of these analyses was used to establish the compression behaviour of the samples. All laboratory experiment was carried according to the suggested method given by British Standard Institute method for testing soils BS1377. (1990) and the America Society for Testing Measurements (ASTM, 2001) standards.

3.2.1 Index and Physical Property

The principal physical properties of interest are volumetric properties such as specific gravity of soil sample, moisture content, density, gradation property, liquid limit and shrinkage limit, the plastic limit could not determine because the soil is highly sandy. The soils were classified using Unified Soil Classification System.

3.2.1.1 Specific gravity

The specific gravity of a substance is defined as the density of the material divided by the density of water at 4°C. It can be expressed as the ratio of the mass of a given volume of soil at a test temperature, to the mass of an equal volume of water at the same temperature. The specific gravity of soil was determined in accordance to BS 1377 (1990). The equation 3.1 was used to calculate the specific gravity.

$$G_s = \frac{(M_1 - M_1)}{(M_4 - M_1) - (M_3 - M_2)} \quad 3.1$$

where M_1 = mass of empty jar + lid, M_2 = mass of jar + lid + oven dry soil, M_3 = mass of jar + lid + soil + water, M_4 = mass of jar + lid + water only.

3.2.1.2 Moisture content determination

The moisture content of each of the intact soil samples collected was determined. Natural moisture content of soils is a time variant parameter which will depend to a large extent on the seasonal levels of surface and subsurface water. The test was done in order to know the amount of moisture present in the natural state. The water content of a soil is expressed as the ratio of the mass of water present to the total mass of the dry sample, it was obtained mathematically as shown equation 3.2.

$$W_n = \frac{M_2 - M_3}{M_2 - M_1} \quad 3.2$$

Where, W_n = moisture content, M_2 = mass of wet soil, M_3 = oven dried mass of the soil, M_1 = mass of the empty can.

3.2.1.3 Particle size distribution

The particle size distribution of the samples was determined using a combination of wet sieving and sedimentation technique (Okewale 2020b, 2020c, 2021). Representative tar sands were firstly soaked with dispersant, Sodium Hexametaphosphate solution ($(\text{NaPO}_3)_6$) and then washed on sieve No. 230 (0.063mm) and the retained soil was air-dried for three days. The air-dried soil sample of known weight was put in the set of stack sieves and then placed on a mechanical shaker Lo sieve for about 10 minutes. The weight of the materials remaining on each sieve was noted and the percentage retained computed as a percentage of the total weight. The percentage passing and cumulative percentage passing were computed for each sieve. The passing samples at the sieve No.230 after washing was poured into a

1000ml cylindrical jar for sedimentation test for silt and clay sized particles quantitative determination. Enough water was added to make 1000ml of suspension and the deflocculant sodium-metaphosphate was used and also another 1000ml cylindrical jar filled up with distilled water and deflocclant in which it is was used as control reading. The suspension was mixed thoroughly by placing a bung on the open end of the jar and turning upside down and back few times. The jar was placed on the cable. The hydrometer was inserted into the suspension jar and the control jar, and the hydrometer readings was taken are 0.5min, 1min, 2min, 5min, 15min, 30min, 60min, 120min, 480min, and 1440min.

3.2.1.4 Liquid limit

This is the water content above which the soil behaves like a viscous liquid (a soil-water mixture with no measurable shear strength). The liquid limit testing apparatus used was cone penetrometer and it was determined according to the recommendation in BS 1377: Part 2: 1990.

3.2.1.5 Linear shrinkage

Linear shrinkage is the decrease in length of a soil sample when oven-dried, starting with a moisture content of the sample at the liquid limit. The linear shrinkage was determined as specified in ASTM. (2001) D-427.

3.2.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM&EDS) Test

Phenom ProX scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with electron dispersive spectrometer (EDS) was used for microstructure and chemical analyses, (Okewale 2020a, 2020b, 2021). The samples tested were taken by breaking surfaces, placed in sample holder and inserted into computer-controlled sample stage (Okewale 2020a, 2021). The optical system monitored focusing and controlling of electron beam. The SEM was equipped with

electron detectors (backscattered and secondary) and CeB6 electron source which gives quality imaging performance. The backscattered gives sharp images and provides chemical contrast information, and secondary collects low energy electrons from surface layer of the samples, it then generates a signal that is displayed on the viewing and recording monitor (Okewale 2020a, 2021). The EDS allows the quantitative chemical analysis to be conducted on the sample by analysing interacted electron beam. The element identification (EID) software package allows the elements to be identified within the sample using the spotmode analysis.

3.2.3 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Test

X ray diffraction analyses were carried out on the samples to determine the mineralogy using X ray diffractometer machine. Samples were air-dried for 1 week and then pulverised. The sample was prepared using the principle of sedimentation and placed in sample holder and pushed in the machine for analysis (Okewale 2020b, 2021). A Shimadzu XDS 2400H diffractometer with an automatic divergence slit equipped with JCPDFWIN software was used for the mineralogical analysis of the sample. The equipment operated at 40 kV and 55 mA, and the minerals were identified in the range of $5^{\circ} \leq 2\theta \leq 80^{\circ}$ with Cu- $K\alpha$ radiation (Okewale 2020b, 2021). The prepared samples were scanned at an interval of $0.02^{\circ}/0.30$ s. The samples were analysed in powder form (Okewale 2020b,2021).

3.2.4 One Dimensional Compression Test (Oedometer Test)

The intact and reconstituted behaviour of the tar sand samples were investigated in one-dimensional compression by carrying out oedometer tests using conventional front loading oedometer, 50mm diameter of 20mm height fixed confining ring was used for the reconstituted samples, 30mm diameter of 20mm height floating ring type was used for the

intact samples (Okewale 2020b, 2021). The ring used for intact samples is a floating ring type which allows higher stresses to be reached and also reduces wall friction (Okewale and Coop 2017; Okewale 2020b, 2021). And also, the effects of structure were determined from the intact behaviour from the graph of specific volume against the effective stress of the tar sand. Reconstituted or disturbed samples are those that have been destructured, in other words, the structure (bonding and intact fabrics) has been removed and the original shape and sizes of the grains has been altered (Okewale 2020b, 2021). The samples were placed and mixed in container and then vibrated for about 30 min to allow the air bubbles to escape. The samples were then placed in the oedometer rings and the initial height carefully measured under a small nominal load. The samples were then flooded and 12 to 24 h were allowed for full saturation before incremental loading to 56kg. Reconstituted samples were prepared by using their natural water content without any additional water. This is because the samples had considerable amount of water in-situ and were still retaining their in-situ water content from the field, the samples were gotten from wet locations. The samples were not prepared to any target initial density or water content. Closed base ring allows moist weight of samples to be taken (Okewale 2020b), inhibits water loss at the base of ring at the end of the tests and does not require use of filter paper which is a major source of inaccuracy in the estimation of initial specific volume (Okewale 2020b, 2021).

The intact samples were prepared by carefully trimming the block samples. The trimming process should minimize sample disturbance. The sample was cut into a small piece using hand held hack saw. The sample was then excavated ahead of the ring. The load was applied in an incremental manner, starting from 0.5kg to 56kg (Okewale, 2020a).

3.2.4.1 Determination of specific volume

The specific volume was determined from the parameters gotten from the oedometer test. In order to give detail description of the behaviour of materials together with stress, specific volume v ($v = 1 + e$, where e is void ratio) serves as an important parameter. The specific volumes were determined using different methods in order to improve the confidence in the measurements. Okewale, 2020a, 2020b, 2021, Okewale and Grobler, 2020; Okewale and Coop, 2017 were able to established different formulas for calculating both the initial specific volume and final specific volume, these four different equations of v were made to be as independent as possible (Okewale 2020b), these formulas were adopted for this study. The initial specific volumes of the samples were derived from sample weight, initial dimensions (height and diameter) and water content. The final specific volumes were estimated from final weight, dimensions and water content, back calculating the initial value using the volumetric strain measured in the tests, this volumetric strain was obtained by dividing the overall settlement by the average initial height, as shown in equation 3.3 to 3.6.

$$v_i = \frac{\gamma_w(1+w_i)G_s}{\gamma_{bi}} \quad 3.3$$

$$v_i = \frac{\gamma_w(1+w_f)G_s}{\gamma_{bf}(1-\varepsilon_v)} \quad 3.4$$

$$v_i = W_i G_s + 1 \quad 3.5$$

$$v_i = \frac{w_f G_s + 1}{(1-\varepsilon_v)} \quad 3.6$$

where v_i = initial specific volume, G_s = specific gravity, w_i = initial water content, w_f = final water content, γ_w = unit weight of water, γ_{bi} = initial bulk unit weight, γ_{bf} = final bulk unit weight and ε_v = vertical strain.

3.2.5 Uniaxial Compressive Strength

The strength property of the tar sand samples from the four locations considered in this study were investigated by carrying out unconfined compressive strength (UCS) test, this test apparently determines the ability of the soil sample to withstand failure by compression. The reconstituted samples of the material were subjected to testing by crushing, the samples were remoulded into a cylindrical mode, that has a diameter of 30mm and height 80mm as shown in plate 3.2 and 3.3, it was then subjected to axial load in a uniaxial compression test machine test and the load that caused the failure of the moulded samples was divided by the cross-sectional area of the specimen and the strength of the soil was determined following the procedure in BS 1377: Part 2: 1990.(Plates 3.2 and 3.3).

Compacted Tar sand Sample

Cylindrical Mode for UCS

Remoulded Tar Sands Samples
Ready for Testing tied Nylons

Plate 3.2 UCS Cylindrical Mode for Reconstituted Sample

Plate 3.3 Molded UCS Samples for Crushing

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Physical and Index Property

4.1.1 Specific Gravity and Moisture Content

The G_s was determined using gas jar method. The specific gravity of the samples ranges between 2.26 – 2.72. RJ has the highest value of specific gravity which was 2.72, while GB has the lowest G_s as shown in table 4.1. The range of specific gravity of the sample are similar to some other studies (e.g., Akinbinu 2003, Afeni 2003, Ola 1991, and Adedimila 1987). The natural water content of the samples was determined using oven-drying method. The natural water content ranges between within 4.7% - 25.6% as presented in table 4.1. LU has a very high natural moisture content compare to other samples, was due to the wet condition of the material when collected.

4.1.2 Particle Size Distributions

The gradings were determined by using a combination of wet sieving and sedimentation technique (Okewale 2020b, 2020c, 2021). The grain size curves of the samples for all the locations studied are shown in Figure 4.1 to 4.4. The grain size curves of sample RJ, TM and LU are similar, this is due to the close range of there grading parameter as shown in table 4.2, but the grain size curve of GB samples was different from the others as shown in Figure 4.3.

Table 4.1 Specific Gravity and Moisture Content Values

Samples	Specific Gravity (Gs)	Moisture Content (%)
RJ	2.52	8.53
TM	2.29	18
GB	2.34	5.8
LU	2.44	25.6

Figures 4.1 Grain Size Distribution Curve for RJ Samples

Figure 4.3 Grain Size Distribution Curve for TM Samples

Figure 4.3 Grain Size Distribution Curve for GB Samples

Figure 4.4 Grain Size Distribution Curve for LU Samples

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Table 4.2 presents the summary of the grading parameters for all samples. According to unified soil classification system, GB, TM and LU are classified as coarse grained soil (CGS)

and well graded (SW). RJ samples are classified as coarse soil and poorly graded soil (SP), this classification is determined based on the values of coefficient of uniformity (C_u) as shown in table 4.1 ($C_u > 4$ is SW and < 4 is SP). LU samples has high fraction of gravel than others. The sand fraction for all the samples is relatively similar. The samples have high sand fraction which is similar to some other studies (e.g., Ifelola, 2019; Akinbinu, 2003; Afeni, 2003, Ola, 1991; and Enu, 1985). From Table 4.2, the percentage of fine sands ranges as 61.1%-67.7%, 38.4%-55.0% 60.4%-76.1%, 27.4%-44.4 for RJ, TM, GB and LU respectively. The percentage of fines (0.0075mm-0.002mm), which is the mixture of silt and clay ranges as, 6.1%-6.8%, 8.6%-10.7%, 4.5%-12.7%, 7.2%- 8.6% for RJ TM, GB and LU samples respectively as shown in table 4.2. It was observed that the clay fraction of LU samples is the same for all depths, but varies for other samples.

Table 4.2 Summary of Grading Parameters

Sample s	Gravel (>4.75m m)	Sand (4.75-0.075mm)			Fines (0.0075-<0.002mm)		Coefficient of Uniformity (C _u)	USCS Classification
	Gravel (%)	Coarse Sand (%)	Medium Sand (%)	Fine Sand (%)	Silt (%) (0.075-0.002mm)	Clay (%) (<0.002mm)		
RJ 1	0.1	4.3	27.6	61.1	1.5	4.6	2.34	CGS/SP
RJ 2	0.1	3.9	28.1	63.5	2.8	3.6	2.62	CGS/SP
RJ 3	0.1	3.9	21.5	67.7	3.2	3.6	2.64	CGS/SP
GB 1	1.8	25.5	25.7	38.4	5.6	3.0	34.1	CGS/SW
GB 2	1.6	25.9	22.2	39.8	7.5	2.9	27	CGS/SW
GB 3	0.1	9.2	24.9	55.0	7.8	2.9	19.2	CGS/SW
TM 1	2.5	18.6	14.1	60.4	0.7	3.8	5.48	CGS/SW
TM 2	2.0	10.7	17.0	63.7	2.8	3.7	6.18	CGS/SW
TM 3	1.6	5.6	3.9	76.1	8.6	4.1	4.41	CGS/SW
LU 1	11.7	26.3	27.7	27.1	4.5	2.7	6.84	CGS/SW
LU 2	11.9	21.0	18.1	41.4	4.9	2.7	6.3	CGS/SW
LU 3	5.8	21.2	20.1	44.4	5.9	2.7	5.55	CGS/SW

USCS= Unified soil classification system, CGS = Coarse grained soil, SP = Poorly graded sands, SW = Well graded sands. (note: C_u >4 is SW while C_u <4 is SP according to USCS classification).

The variation of coefficient of uniformity (C_u) with depth is presented in Figure. 4.5a, the line of demarcation indicates well graded samples. Only GB samples are well graded that, the other samples are classified as poorly graded. The C_u has no trend with depth for LU and TM samples, while C_u decreases with depth for GB samples, and increase with depth for RJ samples. According to unified soil classification system (USCS) the soil mixture for GB, LU and TM samples are well graded, for RJ samples they are poorly graded, this is determined based on their coefficient of uniformity value, but they are all classified as coarse to medium fine silty sand. Figure 4.5b presents the plot of mean particle size (D_{50}) against depth, the estimated average line is presented. The D_{50} of the sample from location GB is slightly smaller than those from location RJ, LU & TM. This can be linked to higher clay and silt fractions, but all of them slightly decreases with depth, similar to related materials (e.g., Okewale and Coop 2017, 2020).

Figure 4.5c shows the variations of fines content (fc), which is a combination of clay and silt fractions with depth. For the samples from all the locations, fines content increases with depth, which supposed to be so base on geological process as fine particles have higher settlement than coarse particle. Samples from locations TM and GB have higher fines content than those from location LU and RJ.

The variation of coefficient of curvature (C_c) is presented in Figure 4.5d the estimated average line is given in the plot, no unique trend with depth for RJ samples, but there is slight decrease of C_c with depth for LU, TM and GB samples.

Figure 4.5e shows the plot of the sand fractions with depth for all the samples, apart for LU samples that slightly decrease with depth, the samples do not have particular trend with

depth. Generally, as the geological processes increase and grading becomes finer, the grading descriptors; D_{50} increases, C_u reduces and fines content reduces with depth.

4.1.3 Liquid Limit and Shrinkage Limit

The liquid limit (LL) was determined by using cone penetrometer method. This method was adopted due to the properties of this material used, more than 50% of the soil component is of sand fraction. The materials are classified as sandy-soil, and the soil is highly non-plastic. Shrinkage limit was also determined and the values are presented in table 4.3 below. The LL of the samples range from 20.4%-23.9% as shown in table 4.3, and according to Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), the calculated range indicated that the soil is classified as silt and clay of low compressibility which represented as ML, the LL values are relatively similar for all the samples which is in agreement with the gradings of the samples. The linear shrinkage ranged between 6 and 10 cm, linear shrinkage value for all samples are in close range.

The variation of LL with depth is presented in Figure 4.5f. The LL values for all samples is relatively similar, so there is no peculiar trend with depth for all the samples.

Table 4.3. Liquid Limit and Linear Shrinkage Values

Samples	Liquid Limit (%)	Linear Shrinkage (cm)
RJ1	21.7	8
RJ2	20.4	7
RJ3	-	-
TM1	23.0	10
TM2	22.3	8
TM3	21.4	9
GB1	23.8	8
GB2	23.1	7
GB3	-	-
LU1	23.1	6
LU2	22.1	7
LU3	21.9	8

Figure 4.5 Variation of Physical and Index Properties with Depth

4.2 MICROSTRUCTURAL AND CHEMICAL ANALYSES

4.2.1 Microstructure of the Samples

The microstructure and composition of the samples were determined using SEM equipped with EDS. Figure 4.6 presents the micrographs of the RJ reconstituted samples. Figure 4.6a shows the microstructure of sample RJ1 and the image as shown for 100 μm field of view. The image is composed of angular particles forming clusters. The clusters and particles are not orientated in a particular direction. These clusters are separated by larger pores. The microstructure of sample RJ3 was also presented in Figure 4.6b and its micrograph is also shown for 100 μm field of view. The fabric was characterised by well-arranged angular particles agglomerated to form continuous clusters, with larger inter-cluster voids. The fabric was generally homogeneous, similar to what have been observed in Athabasca oil sands (e.g., Dusseault and Morgenstern, 1978; Doan, 2011; and Doan et al., 2012). Figure 4.7 presents the microstructures of samples for GB. The clusters are separated smaller pores. The fabric was homogenous, similar to what was observed in location RJ, but with few inter clusters voids. The adherence between bitumen and sand grains was also attested by the observation of various bitumen coated grains. It was observed in SEM images as shown in Figure 4.6 and 4.7, that bitumen seems to bind the grains together.

Figure 4.8a and 4.8b presents the SEM images of the samples from location TM. TM1 the fabric was dominated by angular grains and some grains are aggregated to form clusters. There were few inter particle and intra clusters voids. TM3 the fabric was characterized by grain aggregation forming continuous clusters with few inter cluster voids. The particles in TM1 were finer than TM3.

Figure 4.9a and 4.9b presents the SEM images of samples from LU. The fabrics were similar to the SEM images observed from TM samples. Bitumen was either bonding or coating the sand grains. Voids that correspond to a less dense medium were filled by gas. The image shows some dense areas composed of angular grains (light grey). No specific particle orientation in LU3 and the fabric was characterized by continuous cluster with few inter and intra cluster voids. The SEM images were similar to that obtained by Pierre *et al.*, (2013) and Wong (2003) from back scattered SEM images.

Microscopic observations of the fabric of reconstituted samples from the SEM micrographs were shown in Figure 4.10a, 4.10b, 4.10c, and 4.10d. The micrographs shown were of 100 μm field of view. The reconstitution process produces fairly similar fabrics with their intact samples. Fabrics seem relatively homogenous as observed in their intact samples.

Figure 4.6 SEM Image of Intact Samples for RJ. (a is RJ1 and b RJ3)

Figure 4.7 SEM Image of Intact Samples for GB (a is GB1 and b GB3)

Figure 4.8 SEM image of intact samples for TM. (a is TM1 and b TM3)

Figure 4.9 SEM image of intact samples for LU. (a is LU1 and b LU3)

Figure. 4.10 SEM Image of Reconstituted Samples for RJ 2 (a) and GB 2 (b)

Figure. 4.11 SEM Image of Reconstituted Samples from TM 2(c) and LU (d)

4.2.2 Chemical Compositions of the Sample

Table 4 shows the details of chemical composition obtained from EDS analysis incorporated into SEM for the selected samples. Chemical analysis is important for the characterization of materials employing the combination of elemental oxides (Okewale and Coop 2018b; Okewale 2020a; Okewale 2021). Chemical analyses were done for the samples as presented in Table 4.5. The values of silica are highest followed by alumina for all the samples and other chemical oxides in smaller percentages. Again, the considerable amount of silica and alumina for all samples signify the presence of clay minerals, quartz and sakhaite in the tar sands. The average values of silica and alumina give direct similarities to the values of silicon and aluminium for the soils as discussed earlier but with different numerical values. No particular trend of silica and alumina with depth, but silica is high in RJ samples than others, while alumina is high in LU than others. The chemical composition of the tar sands investigated is similar to that of Athabasca oil sand deposit in Canada (Pierre et al., 2013 and Doan et al., 2012)

4.3 Mineralogical Details

Table 4.4 presents the details of mineralogy of the samples as obtained from X-ray diffraction. The minerals present are; quartz, maralite, sakhaite, graphite, clinochlore, kaolinites, illites and some other unnamed minerals. Quartz and maralite are silicate minerals, sakahaite and graphite are borate carbon mineral, clinochlore chlorite mineral while kaolinites and illites are clay minerals. Quartz dominates the mineralogy which was similar to the chemical composition of the samples. TM has the highest percentage of quartz (61%) followed by LU (60%), RJ (52%), and GB (42.4%). Kaolinites are very stable with strong structures, absorb little water and possess low swelling behaviour (Omomomi 2020). Kaolinites is slightly higher in samples from location TM followed by location RJ,

but it was observed that LU has small clay minerals (kaolinites and illite) and is the lowest among all the samples. According to Ola (1991), clay mineral increases the strength of material most especially kaolinite because it acts binder in soil composition (e.g., Omomomi, 2020). It can be said that mineralogy has a great influence on the strength of this material. The sample with highest clay mineral (kaolinite) has the highest value of compressive strength, similar to what was reported for clay and tar sand (e.g., Omomomi 2020; Ola 1991). The presence of graphite and sakahaite in GB indicates that the samples is highly rich in borate carbon mineral more than others, and based on this results, GB sample is best location to be selected for mining bitumen in Ondo state.

Table 4.4 Details of Mineralogy of the Samples

Samples	Minerals							Others (%)
	Quartz (%)	Marialite (%)	Kaolinite (%)	Illite (%)	Clinochole (%)	Sakhaite (%)	Graphite (%)	
RJ	52	0.2	14.5	6.9	7.9	17	-	1.5
TM	61	0.6	21.9	10	6.1	0.2	-	-
GD	42.5	16	8.7	18.9	-	8.1	4.9	0.9
LU	60	13.6	3.5	5.2	6.1	-	-	11.2

Table 4.5 Details of Chemical Composition of the Samples

SAMPLES	SiO₂ (%)	Al₂O₃ (%)	Fe₂O₃ (%)	SO₂ (%)	K₂O (%)	Nb₂O₅ (%)	Y₂O₃ (%)	Ag₂O (%)	CaO (%)	Mg O (%)	TiO₂ (%)
RJ 1	70.6 2	5.32	2.59	4.0 1	1.78	2.10	1.83	1.22	1.35	0.71	0.0
RJ 2	70.6 4	5.10	1.10	4.2 8	1.02	2.33	1.95	0.87	0.87	0.73	0.86
RJ 3	54.0 8	7.71	4.53	9.1 5	1.35	2.67	2.14	1.57	1.16	0.99	0.96
GB 1	52.3 5	12.98	5.76	8.8 4	1.41	1.94	1.40	1.20	0.77	0.83	0.67
GB 2	54.1 8	9.67	2.40	7.6 7	1.56	2.30	2.05	1.39	1.29	1.21	0.92
GB 3	46.2 2	8.77	4.85	8.7 4	1.72	3.45	2.00	2.65	1.25	1.14	0.0
TM 1	51.8 0	18.5	12.53	1.1 3	1.98	1.85	1.65	1.34	3.46	1.21	2.21
TM 2	59.4 2	16.68	7.77	0.9 8	2.41	1.30	1.89	0.88	2.93	0.76	3.08
TM 3	55.7 1	18.59	10.18	0.6 8	2.22	1.71	1.61	1.27	2.33	0.73	2.95
LU 1	56.8 4	14.69	10.40	2.1 5	1.55	2.36	1.55	1.47	1.51	0.81	1.39
LU 2	57.3 5	20.36	10.12	1.2 6	1.87	1.03	1.23	1.05	0.63	0.50	2.49
LU 3	49.6 7	24.54	4.91	2.1 3	2.38	1.89	2.41	2.21	1.10	0.81	4.47

4.4 Behaviour of Reconstituted Samples

Figure 4.12a, 4.12b, 4.12c and 4.12d present one-dimensional compression behaviour for the reconstituted samples. The compression behaviour of reconstituted soil is termed intrinsic behaviour (Okewale, 2020). This behaviour results solely from the constituent particles of the soil (Okewale 2020). The details of oedometer tests are given in Table 4.6. In the test descriptions, the first two letters indicate sample location, followed by state of the samples (reconstituted and intact) and the test number. The initial and final specific volumes, the vertical effective stress at the end of compression as well as accuracy of specific volume are included in the table. Figure 4.12(a) presents the compression paths of the RJ samples. These start at different initial specific volumes and samples at different depths define separate NCLs. For given depth, the compression curves converge to a unique line, similar to clays (e.g., Burland 1990; Gasparre and Coop 2008; Mataic et al. 2015; Okewale 2020) and other related materials (e.g., Okewale and Coop 2017; Rocchi et al. 2015, 2017; Okewale 2019c). The compression curves for RJ 2 plot above RJ 1 and RJ 3 due to high specific volume. The curves of RJ 2 are flatter than others, and the difference between the initial and final specific volume is very small. This can be attributed to the stiffness of this sample. Figure 4.12b shows the compression behaviour GB samples and the compression curves converge to a unique line similar to RJ samples. Figure 4.12c shows the compression paths for the TM samples. Compression curves are fairly similar and they all converge to a unique line. Figure 4.12d shows the compression paths for LU samples and there is no difference in the compression curves compared to that of GB. The samples also have convergence behaviour. Except for the RJ, all samples have similar compression curves, which was related to compression curves of the Canadian bituminous sands. (e.g., Dusseault, 1980 and Pierre et al., 2013). Figure 4.13a, 4.13b, 4.13c, and 4.13d

presents the summary of the one-dimensional normal compression lines (1D-NCLs) of the samples. The 1D-NCLs refer to the intrinsic behaviour derived from reconstituted samples (Gasparre and Coop 2008; Okewale 2021). Normal compression line (NCL) was estimated using compressibility parameters (intercept N and compressibility index C_c). Within the range of stresses tested, the 1D-NCLs are assumed straight lines, similar to (Okewale and Coop 2020, Okewale 2020; Okewale and Grobler 2020). It can be seen that the slope of the NCLs is relatively similar as shown in Figure 4.13 (a) to 4.13 (d). Samples with high fine content plot above the low fines, Figure 4.13(a) and 4.13(b) for RJ and GB, as it expected that the finer sample will plot above (Okewale 2020). But contrast is seen for TM and LU samples, this may be due to their mineralogy and microstructure. This has been found by other studies (e.g., Chow et al., 2018; Ng et al., 2019; and Okewale, 2020). Figure 4.13 shows the NCLs of the GB samples, and the behaviour which is similar to that of RJ, but with no peculiar trend with depth.

The compressibility of the samples is determined in terms of slope (λ) and the intercepts (N_o). The λ is obtained from the compressibility index (C_c) as $\lambda = C_c/2.303$ and N_o is the intercepts of the NCL at 1 kPa. The parameters are estimated from NCLs shown in figure 4.13. The variations of the compressibility parameters with depth are presented in Figure 4.14a and 4.14b. For all the samples considered estimated average lines are shown for both parameters. Figure 4.14a and 4.14b shows that the parameters for three samples (LU, GB, TM) have direct similarities and they have no trend with depth, but for RJ the slope (λ) decrease slightly with depth. The parameters are expected to reduce with depth based on geological processes. Compared to other studies on different materials (e.g., Pieere et al., 2013; Gasparre and Coop 2008; Mataic et al. 2015), the samples in this study

have lower compressibility and this is due to the presence of higher sand fractions, low liquid limit (LL) and different mineralogy.

Table 4.6 Details of the Oedometer Tests

Samples	Test description	v_o	v_f	σ'_{vmax} (kPa)	Accuracy of v (\pm)
RJ 1	RJ 1 r	1.7960	1.7018	3076	0.130
	RJ 1-r2	1.6242	1.5605	3076	0.060
	RJ 1-r3	1.5974	1.5473	3076	0.053
	RJ 1-r4	1.6478	1.5314	3076	0.070
	RJ 1-r5	1.5595	1.4991	3076	0.054
	RJ 1-r6	1.5184	1.4567	3076	0.051
	RJ 1-i1	1.6326	1.4039	8547	0.020
	RJ 1 i2	1.2637	1.1940	8547	0.014
	RJ 1-i3	1.7034	1.6915	8547	0.104
	RJ 1-i4	1.5493	1.3491	8547	0.008
	RJ 1-i5	1.6112	1.5597	8547	0.094
	RJ 1-i6	1.3848	1.3714	8547	0.006
	RJ 2	RJ 2-r1	1.8857	1.8693	3076
RJ 2-r2		1.8025	1.7900	3076	0.180
RJ 2-r3		1.8750	1.8510	3076	0.130
RJ 2-r4		2.0190	1.9723	3076	0.220
RJ 2-r5		1.9427	1.9120	3076	0.200
RJ 2-i1		1.5623	1.4451	8547	0.100
RJ 2-i2		1.3754	1.3366	8547	0.080
RJ 2-i3		1.3163	1.2794	8547	0.010
RJ 2-i4		1.4429	1.4358	8547	0.104
RJ 3	RJ 3 r1	1.8259	1.7935	3076	0.190
	RJ 3 r2	1.7042	1.5744	3076	0.130
	RJ 3 r3	1.6538	1.6319	3076	0.120
	RJ 3 r4	1.8777	1.8383	3076	0.170
	RJ 3 i1	1.3087	1.2227	8547	0.050
	RJ 3 i2	1.5325	1.4620	8547	0.090
	RJ 3 i3	1.5179	1.5046	8547	0.085
	RJ 3 i4	1.5213	1.5043	8547	0.080
GB 1	GB 1 r1	1.8285	1.3288	3076	0.061
	GB 1 r2	1.6958	1.3864	3076	0.072
	GB 1 i1	1.2929	1.1618	8547	0.011
	GB 1 i2	1.4423	1.2575	8547	0.041
GB 2	GB 2 r1	1.7298	1.2687	3076	0.013
	GB 2 r2	1.6670	1.3423	3076	0.058
	GB 2 i1	1.3417	1.2003	8547	0.023
	GB 2 i2	1.3135	1.1950	8547	0.044
GB 3	GB 3 r1	1.7265	1.4560	3076	0.036
	GB 3 r2	1.7127	1.2982	3076	0.085
	GB 3 i1	1.4165	1.1416	8547	0.021
	GB 3 i2	1.4655	1.2254	8547	0.019

Samples	Test description	v_o	v_f	σ'_{vmax} (kPa)	Accuracy of v (\pm)
TM 1	TM 1 r1	1.7386	1.4914	3076	0.062
	TM 1-r2	1.6360	1.3668	3076	0.071
	TM 1-r3	1.6781	1.3668	3076	0.077
	TM 1-r4	1.8899	1.4189	3076	0.041
	TM 1-r5	1.7531	1.5575	3076	0.016
	TM 1-i1	1.4874	1.1126	8547	0.050
	TM 1 i2	1.6268	1.2303	8547	0.079
	TM 1-i3	1.5272	1.3678	8547	0.077
	TM 1 i4	1.7042	1.3446	8547	0.077
TM 2	TM 2-r1	1.7042	1.3029	3076	0.069
	TM 2-r2	1.5854	1.3029	3076	0.080
	TM 2-r3	1.5264	1.3694	3076	0.014
	TM 2-r4	1.6391	1.3247	3076	0.084
	TM 2-r5	1.6905	1.3440	3076	0.079
	TM 2-i1	1.6385	1.3698	8547	0.033
	TM 2-i2	1.7426	1.4348	8547	0.010
	TM 2-i3	1.6262	1.3007	8547	0.088
	TM 2-i4	1.6574	1.3058	8547	0.056
TM 3	TM 3 r1	1.4448	1.0837	3076	0.034
	TM 3 r2	1.5093	1.2397	3076	0.036
	TM 3 r3	1.6166	1.3062	3076	0.058
	TM 3 r4	1.5212	1.2509	3076	0.059
	TM 3 r5	1.6223	1.2206	3076	0.100
	TM 3 i1	1.4669	1.4246	8547	0.029
	TM 3 i2	1.5244	1.3097	8547	0.007
	TM 3 i3	1.5715	1.3277	8547	0.033
	TM 3 i4	1.5232	1.1607	8547	0.069
LU 1	LU 1 r1	2.0704	1.5196	3076	0.074
	LU 1 r2	2.2270	1.4589	3076	0.027
	LU 1 r3	2.1459	1.8104	3076	0.093
	LU 1 i1	2.0322	1.6331	8547	0.011
	LU 1 i2	1.7285	1.3717	8547	0.093
LU 3	LU 1 i3	1.8475	1.5017	8547	0.058
	LU 3 r1	1.7744	1.3841	3076	0.077
	LU 3 r2	1.9584	1.4896	3076	0.053
	LU 3 r3	1.8220	1.4109	3076	0.080
	LU 3 i1	1.8478	1.5355	8547	0.030
	LU 3 i2	1.7692	1.5908	8547	0.080
	LU 3 i3	1.8520	1.6258	8547	0.038

r reconstituted, i intact, v_o initial specific volume, v_f final specific volume, δ'_v vertical effective stress at the end of compression, v specific volume, RJ1, RJ2, RJ3, GB1, GB2, GB3, TM1, TM2, TM3, LU1, LU2, LU3 represent the samples used, r1 to r6 indicate reconstituted tests, while i1 to i4 indicate intact tests.

Figure.4.12 Reconstituted Compression Curves (a) is RJ, (b) GB, (c) TM, and (d) LU

Figure 4.13 Summary of ID-NCLs (a) is RJ, (b) GB, (c) TM, and (d) LU

Figure. 4.14 Variation of Compressibility Parameters and Mechanical Properties with Depth

4.5 Intact Samples Behaviour and The Effects of Structure

4.5.1 Behaviour of Intact Samples

Figure 4.15a, 4.15b, 4.15c and 4.15d presents the behaviour of intact samples in one-dimensional compression. The details of the sample are shown in Table 4.6. The compression paths of samples from the same depth are relatively similar. Samples are grouped according to the depths for each location. The in situ specific volume (v) varies from 1.292 to 1.867. Samples with high in situ specific volume plot above those with low in situ specific volume. Samples from LU has the highest in situ specific volume while those from GB have the lowest in situ specific volume. The yield stress (σ'_y) of the samples were obtained using Casagrande construction. Yield stress here means that the maximum stress at which samples be subjected to without any large strain (Okewale 2021). Only the compression paths of GB plot below NCL and this was due to low in situ specific volume as shown in Figure 4.15b. Figure 4.14d present the variation of in situ specific volume (v) with depth. Samples from location TM have the highest value of in situ specific volume. And values of v for GB samples have a relationship with the depth, in situ specific volume of GB samples increases with depth as shown in figure 4.13d, other samples have no particular trend with depth. The yield stress of the samples ranges between 75 kPa and 600 kPa. The variations of yield stress with depth is presented in figure 4.14c. Yield stress for GB samples increases with depth, for LU it decreases with depth. For TM and RJ samples yield stress value varies, no trend with depth.

Figure 4.15 Intact Compression Curves. (a) is RJ, (b) GB, (c) TM, and (d) LU

4.5.2 Effects of Structure

Increase in stiffness of materials due to bonding and fabric during one-dimensional compression loading process is referred to as the effects of structure (Okewale 2020a, 2021). For this study, samples in its intact state in which bonding and fabric depend on the geological history of the sample is termed to be structure (Okewale 2020b, 2021). Apart from GB samples, all other samples were observed to have cross the intrinsic normal compression line. GB samples do not cross the ICL due to low initial v . Sample with highest initial in situ specific volumes seems to cross 1D-NCL at a very high vertical stress. The comparison between the behaviour of the intact and reconstituted samples using normalization gives the effects of structure (Okewale and Coop 2017; Gasparre and Coop 2008). By doing this, the effects of grading and mineralogy of samples are normalized (Okewale 2020). Figure 4.16, 4.17, 4.18 and 4.19 shows the normalized compression characteristics of the samples using void index (I_v) normalization proposed by (Burland 1990). The I_v is stated as:

$$I_v = \frac{e - e^*_{100}}{e^*_{100} - e^*_{1000}} \quad 4.1$$

where e , e^*_{100} , and e^*_{1000} are current void ratio, void ratio on 1D-NCL at vertical stress of 100 kPa and void ratio at vertical stress of 1000 kPa respectively. At specific volume of 1 ($v = 1$), the I_v will have a limiting value. The compression curves tend to curve when the limiting value is attained. The degree to which the compression paths of the intact samples cross the ICL indicates the influence of structure. It is obvious that the compression paths of GB samples do not cross the ICL, and this can be attributed to lower values of in situ void index (I_v). For other samples RJ, LU, TM their paths

crossed the ICL but not for all the samples, samples with low initial I_v does not cross the ICL. The apparent no effect of structure for the GB samples due to low initial I_v this has also been reported in some other materials like talc, shale, weathered and weak rocks (Okewale, 2021, 2020b, Okewale 2017; Okewale and Coop 2017; 2018a). This has been highlighted by Gasparre and Coop (2008) as an artefact of the void index normalization rather than necessarily a true indication of no effects of structure.

Another quantitative way to determine the effects of structure is by computing stress sensitivity (S_σ), which was the ratio of stress at yield stress (σ'_y) to the stress on ICL at the same specific volume, as proposed by Cotecchia and Chandler (2000). However, the method cannot be used for samples from GB locations because the ICL was defined outside the intact compression curves, but was used for other locations. Figure 4.18a shows the variation of S_σ with depth, and it shows that RJ, LU, and TM samples have positive effects of structure but no particular trend with depth. This was similar to what have been reported for other materials (e.g., Gasparre and Coop 2008; Okewale and Coop 2017, 2018a; Rocchi et al. 2017; Okewale 2020). The effects of structure can either be positive or negative depending on the value of stress sensitivity (Okewale 2021). Positive effect of structure indicates stress sensitivity value of greater than one and the value of less than one signifies negative effect of structure (Okewale, 2021). The effects of structure are higher TM followed by LU. A modified stress sensitivity called pseudo stress sensitivity ($S_{\sigma,10}$) which is 10 times the yield stress (Okewale and Coop 2020, Okewale 2021), was also computed to quantify the effects of structure in the samples.

Figure 4.16 Effects of Structure for RJ Samples using Void Index

Figure 4.17 Effects of Structure for TM Samples using Void Index

Figure 4.18 Effects of Structure for TM Samples using Void Index

Figure 4.19 Effects of Structure for GB Samples using Void Index

Figure. 4.20 Effects of Structure using Stress Sensitivity Analyses for RJ, LU and TM Samples

Figure. 4.21 Definition of Stress Sensitivity (After Okewale & Grobler, 2021)

In order to quantify the effects of structure in GB samples, the alternative stress sensitivity analysis proposed by Okewale and Grobler (2021) was used. Two alternative methods called $S_{\sigma,1}$ and $S_{\sigma,2}$ was developed as shown in equations 4.2 and 4.3. Figure 4.21 presents the schematic plot of the definition of the proposed stress sensitivity. In the two methods, the stress sensitivity was assumed to be the stress at yield for the intact sample divided by the stress on the intrinsic compression line of the reconstituted sample at the same specific volume, similar to other suggested methods (e.g., Cotecchia and Chandler 2000; Mataic *et al.*, 2015).

Stress sensitivity is defined as the yield stress divided by equivalent stress on the ICL at the same specific volume as shown in Figure 4.21

$$S_{\sigma,1} = \frac{\sigma'_y}{\sigma'_{e,1}} \quad 4.2$$

where σ'_y is yield stress and $\sigma'_{e,1}$ is stress on the ICL

$$S_{\sigma,2} = \frac{\sigma'_y}{\sigma'_{e,2}} \quad 4.3$$

where σ'_y is yield stress and $\sigma'_{e,2}$ is stress on the ICL

Applying the first method, the stress sensitivity value ranges between 1.29 and 5.5. This shows that the effect of structure was positive, similar to what has been found for different materials (Okewale, 2019b, 2020b; Okewale and Coop, 2017; 2018a; Okewale and Grobler, 2020b, 2020c; Rocchi *et al.*, 2015). Applying the second method, the stress sensitivity values range between 1.47 and 9.5, and this again shows positive effects of structure. This is however expected based on the definition of the two methods.

4.5.3 Post Yield Behaviour

The destructure of the samples were determined by studying post-yield behaviour. This was achieved by presenting the current values of stress sensitivity with vertical stress as shown in Figure 4.22 (Okewale 2020b). Figure 4.22 presents the destructure of sample using the ICL of the first method of determination of stress sensitivity. The line of demarcation ($S\sigma = 1$) shows the points at which the structure in the sample has completely broken down. It indicates that the samples have been completely destructured at the end of the tests. The second method the post-yield behaviour has direct similarity with the first method.

Figure 4.23 presents the post yield behaviour of RJ, LU and TM samples. Few samples are shown for clarity. This behaviour was quantified by estimating the offset between the intact post-yield compression path and its corresponding ICL at the same specific volume (Okewale, 2021). By doing this, the structure degradation of the intact sample in compression was quantified. For all the samples, the $S\sigma$ values were reducing with stress indicating that the structure was being broken down by straining. It shows that at the highest stresses reached in the tests, the samples have been completely destructured. Within the scatter of the data, the differences between the samples from the three locations and depths are relatively small.

Figure 4.22 Post Yield Behaviour of GB Samples using First Method

Figure 4.23 Post Yield Behaviour of RJ, LU & TM Samples

4.6 Uniaxial Compressive Strength Test

Strength characterization of the tar sand samples obtained from the four locations were investigated by carrying unconfined compression strength (UCS) test, samples were tested after been crushed, remolded and compacted at the same blows per layers with respect to depth. It was observed that the UCS values has a direct relationship to the depth, the strength of the material increases with depth, though there were no much increase in the values shallow depth reached. As shown in the Table 4.6 the UCS values ranges from 28.9 kPa to 52.2 kPa. LU sample has the lowest UCS value at 0.3m depth and TM sample has the highest UCS value at 1.2m depth. The values of the UCS for RJ, TM, GB and LU are all presented in Table 4.7. Ola (1991) reported the compressive strength of the in situ tar sand sample from LU to be 450 kN/m² and remoulded without cured and cured for 7days were 33.5 kN/m² and 83 kN/m² respectively. The UCS for LU for this study ranges from 28.9 kPa – 37.5 kPa which was similar to what was found by Ola (1991). The UCS values slightly increases with depth in all location studied. This can be linked to gradings as earlier discussed. Samples from location TM has the highest UCS values while LU has the lowest UCS values.

Figure 4.24 to 4.27 shows the uniaxial compressive strength graph for all the samples. Compressive strength values were plot against their respective strain values. The highest point reached on the curves for all the samples indicate their UCS values. The UCS curves were similar for all samples, the samples with low UCS values plot below those of high values, values at the highest point the curves represent the highest load the samples can withstand before failing. TM samples has the highest UCS at the

maximum depth reached as shown in Figure 4.25, and LU has the lowest at the maximum depth reached.

Figure 4.10b present the variation of the UCS values with depth for all the samples. It was observed from the plot that the UCS values increases with depth as illustrated by the line of demarcation in the plot.

Table 4.7 Uniaxial Compression Strength Values for the Samples

Samples	UCS (kPa)
RJ 1	41.2
RJ 2	44.6
RJ 3	46.6
TM 1	43.5
TM 2	46.8
TM 3	52.1
GB 1	46.2
GB 2	-
GB 3	50.5
LU 1	29.7
LU 2	-
LU 3	36.3

Figure 4.24 Uniaxial Compressive Strength Graph for RJ Samples

Figure 4.25 Uniaxial Compressive Strength Graph for TM Samples

Figure 4.26 Uniaxial Compressive Strength Graph GB Samples

Figure 4.27 Uniaxial Compressive Strength Graph for LU Samples

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The mechanics of compression behaviour in tar sands have been investigated by conducting several one-dimensional compression tests on the samples obtained from four different locations at different depths in their intact and reconstituted states. Also, classification and index tests were carried out, their mineralogy, microstructure and geochemical characteristics and mechanical properties were investigated. The GB, TM and LU samples are all well-graded with low fine content and higher percentage of sand fraction. RJ sample is poorly graded. The values of C_u for GB and LU decrease with depth and for RJ and TM there is no particular trend with depths. All the samples are non-plastic. The fabrics of the samples are characterized by particles and clusters with inter and intra particle and cluster voids. The chemical composition was dominated by silica oxides followed by alumina and other chemical oxides in smaller percentages. The mineralogy was dominated by quartz, maralite, kaolinites, illite, clinchhole, sakhaite and graphite. Clay minerals have positive influence on the strength of the samples as it was noticed that samples with highest percentage of clay mineral have higher UCS values than the other.

The compression paths of the samples converge to unique line, showing no transitional mode of behaviour. A unique one-dimensional normal compression line (NCL*) was found in reconstituted samples. Apart from GB sample, the intact samples reach a state outside the intrinsic compression line. The compressibility index was similar for samples at each location. The compressibility parameters have no particular trend with depth. In general, the tar sands investigated have low compressibility but those with

high fines content, clay minerals are more compressible. The void index normalization cannot be used to quantify the effects of structure for GB due to low in situ void index. The effects of structure using void index normalization for RJ, TM, LU samples are positive. Applying stress sensitivities analyses effects of structure show positive but small effects of structure for all the samples. The post yield behaviour was studied, and it shows that at the highest stresses reached in the tests, the samples have been completely destructured. From the uniaxial compressive strength tests carried out, it was observed that the strength of the samples increases with depth and this can be linked to their classification properties.

5.2 Recommendations

The work done in this research has been able to provide information about the mechanics of compression behaviour of Ondo State tar sand, this engineering information was actually new for this particular material in Nigeria, unique is the systematic manner in which physical and index properties, microstructure and mineralogy are related to compression behaviour.

Based on the above results, the following recommendation are made:

1. Choice of machinery to be used in the mining stage and when erecting structure at site when mining this material should be based on the compressibility parameters and their yield stress values as investigated, because this material was classified of low compressibility in comparison with some other report of related materials.
2. The compressibility parameters calculated in this research work should use when carrying out engineering design in any of the locations studied.

However, further investigation can still be made in the following areas:

1. Investigate this material at deeper depth so as have a detail understanding about the lithology along depth, and their different engineering behaviour along the vertical profile.
2. Investigate the effect of bitumen on the strength of this material
3. Investigate the compression behaviour the tar sand tailings and it Suitability for construction purpose.

1.5 Contributions to Knowledge

The research work has contributed to knowledge in the following areas:

- a) provided information about the compression behavior of the Ondo State Tar sand;
- b) related index property, mineralogy, chemical and microstructure of Tar sand to compression behaviour;
- c) established the different between reconstituted and intact behaviour of the Ondo state Tar sand.
- d) provided additional information on the engineering characteristics of Irelejare, Gbelejuloda, Temidire, and Ilubirin in Ondo State Nigeria, which will be needed in the extraction of the Tar sands.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1 (SEM & EDS TEST RESULTS)

RJ-P1 OX

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	37.00	46.72	SiO ₂	70.64
O	31.73	22.82		
C	20.01	10.81	C	7.64
Al	3.14	3.82	Al ₂ O ₃	5.10
S	2.10	3.03	SO ₂	4.28
Nb	0.55	2.31	Nb ₂ O ₅	2.33
Y	0.54	2.17	Y ₂ O ₃	1.95
K	0.68	1.19	K ₂ O	1.02
Ag	0.24	1.14	Ag ₂ O	0.87
Fe	0.43	1.09	Fe ₂ O ₃	1.10
Ca	0.49	0.88	CaO	0.87
Cl	0.51	0.81	Cl	0.57
Ti	0.34	0.73	TiO ₂	0.86
Mg	0.57	0.62	MgO	0.73
V	0.25	0.57	V ₂ O ₅	0.72
Na	0.51	0.52	Na ₂ O	0.50
N	0.69	0.43	N	0.31
P	0.23	0.32	P ₂ O ₅	0.51

FOV: 839 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 16:19

RJ-P2 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	37.65	46.35	SiO ₂	70.62
O	33.39	23.42		
C	16.42	8.64	C	6.16
Al	3.34	3.95	Al ₂ O ₃	5.32
S	2.01	2.82	SO ₂	4.01
Fe	1.04	2.55	Fe ₂ O ₃	2.59
K	1.21	2.08	K ₂ O	1.78
Nb	0.51	2.06	Nb ₂ O ₅	2.10
Y	0.52	2.02	Y ₂ O ₃	1.83
Ag	0.34	1.60	Ag ₂ O	1.22
Ca	0.77	1.36	CaO	1.35
Cl	0.81	1.26	Cl	0.90
Mg	0.56	0.60	MgO	0.71
Na	0.49	0.49	Na ₂ O	0.47
P	0.30	0.41	P ₂ O ₅	0.66
N	0.64	0.40	N	0.28
Ti	0.00	0.00	TiO ₂	0.00

FOV: 847 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 10:44

RJ-P3 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	26.03	33.60	SiO ₂	54.08
O	30.46	22.39		
C	27.01	14.91	C	11.22
S	4.13	6.09	SO ₂	9.15
Al	4.37	5.42	Al ₂ O ₃	7.71
Fe	1.64	4.21	Fe ₂ O ₃	4.53
Nb	0.58	2.48	Nb ₂ O ₅	2.67
Y	0.55	2.24	Y ₂ O ₃	2.14
Ag	0.39	1.95	Ag ₂ O	1.57
K	0.83	1.49	K ₂ O	1.35
Ca	0.60	1.10	CaO	1.16
Cl	0.61	0.99	Cl	0.75
Mg	0.71	0.80	MgO	0.99
Ti	0.35	0.77	TiO ₂	0.96
Na	0.61	0.64	Na ₂ O	0.65
N	0.87	0.56	N	0.42
P	0.27	0.38	P ₂ O ₅	0.66

FOV: 839 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 16:24

GB-P1 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	26.71	34.98	SiO ₂	54.18
O	25.75	19.21		
C	31.02	17.37	C	12.58
Al	5.62	7.07	Al ₂ O ₃	9.67
S	3.54	5.30	SO ₂	7.67
Fe	0.89	2.32	Fe ₂ O ₃	2.40
Y	0.54	2.23	Y ₂ O ₃	2.05
Nb	0.51	2.22	Nb ₂ O ₅	2.30
K	0.98	1.79	K ₂ O	1.56
Ag	0.35	1.78	Ag ₂ O	1.39
Ca	0.68	1.27	CaO	1.29
Cl	0.63	1.05	Cl	0.76
Mg	0.89	1.01	MgO	1.21
Ti	0.34	0.76	TiO ₂	0.92
P	0.51	0.74	P ₂ O ₅	1.23
Na	0.58	0.62	Na ₂ O	0.60
N	0.46	0.30	N	0.22

FOV: 839 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 16:06

GB-P2 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	28.73	35.59	SiO ₂	52.35
O	23.71	16.74		
C	26.83	14.21	C	9.77
Al	8.39	9.99	Al ₂ O ₃	12.98
S	4.55	6.43	SO ₂	8.84
Fe	2.38	5.86	Fe ₂ O ₃	5.76
Nb	0.48	1.98	Nb ₂ O ₅	1.94
K	0.99	1.71	K ₂ O	1.41
Ag	0.34	1.63	Ag ₂ O	1.20
Y	0.41	1.60	Y ₂ O ₃	1.40
Cl	0.67	1.05	Cl	0.72
Ca	0.46	0.80	CaO	0.77
Mg	0.68	0.73	MgO	0.83
P	0.46	0.63	P ₂ O ₅	1.00
Ti	0.28	0.58	TiO ₂	0.67
N	0.49	0.30	N	0.21
Na	0.16	0.16	Na ₂ O	0.15

FOV: 838 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 11:07

GB-P3 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	23.28	29.86	SiO ₂	46.22
C	34.97	19.18	C	13.88
O	21.67	15.83		
Al	5.20	6.41	Al ₂ O ₃	8.77
S	4.13	6.05	SO ₂	8.74
Fe	1.84	4.68	Fe ₂ O ₃	4.85
Ag	0.69	3.41	Ag ₂ O	2.65
Nb	0.79	3.33	Nb ₂ O ₅	3.45
Y	0.54	2.17	Y ₂ O ₃	2.00
K	1.10	1.97	K ₂ O	1.72
P	1.11	1.58	P ₂ O ₅	2.61
Cl	0.86	1.40	Cl	1.01
Ca	0.68	1.24	CaO	1.25
Na	1.18	1.24	Na ₂ O	1.21
Mg	0.86	0.95	MgO	1.14
N	1.10	0.70	N	0.51
Ti	0.00	0.00	TiO ₂	0.00

FOV: 848 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 15:43

TM-P1 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	36.39	39.70	SiO ₂	59.42
O	37.36	23.22		
Al	12.04	12.62	Al ₂ O ₃	16.68
Fe	3.58	7.77	Fe ₂ O ₃	7.77
Ca	1.92	2.99	CaO	2.93
K	1.89	2.86	K ₂ O	2.41
Ti	1.42	2.64	TiO ₂	3.08
Y	0.62	2.13	Y ₂ O ₃	1.89
Nb	0.36	1.30	Nb ₂ O ₅	1.30
Ag	0.28	1.16	Ag ₂ O	0.88
S	0.56	0.70	SO ₂	0.98
Cl	0.48	0.66	Cl	0.46
Mg	0.69	0.65	MgO	0.76
Na	0.72	0.64	Na ₂ O	0.60
C	0.93	0.43	C	0.30
N	0.62	0.34	N	0.24
P	0.15	0.18	P ₂ O ₅	0.29

FOV: 838 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 15:08

TM-P2 OX

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	30.82	33.36	SiO ₂	51.80
O	38.50	23.74		
Al	12.73	13.24	Al ₂ O ₃	18.15
Fe	5.61	12.08	Fe ₂ O ₃	12.53
Ca	2.20	3.41	CaO	3.46
K	1.50	2.26	K ₂ O	1.98
Ti	0.99	1.82	TiO ₂	2.21
Y	0.52	1.79	Y ₂ O ₃	1.65
Nb	0.50	1.78	Nb ₂ O ₅	1.85
Ag	0.41	1.71	Ag ₂ O	1.34
C	3.00	1.39	C	1.01
Mg	1.07	1.00	MgO	1.21
S	0.63	0.78	SO ₂	1.13
Cl	0.54	0.74	Cl	0.54
P	0.36	0.43	P ₂ O ₅	0.72
Na	0.41	0.36	Na ₂ O	0.35
N	0.20	0.11	N	0.08

FOV: 845 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 10:49

TM-P3 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	35.05	37.38	SiO ₂	55.71
O	36.15	21.97		
Al	13.79	14.13	Al ₂ O ₃	18.59
Fe	4.82	10.22	Fe ₂ O ₃	10.18
K	1.78	2.65	K ₂ O	2.22
Ti	1.40	2.54	TiO ₂	2.95
Ca	1.57	2.39	CaO	2.33
Y	0.54	1.82	Y ₂ O ₃	1.61
Nb	0.49	1.72	Nb ₂ O ₅	1.71
Ag	0.41	1.70	Ag ₂ O	1.27
Cl	0.71	0.95	Cl	0.66
Mg	0.68	0.63	MgO	0.73
C	1.18	0.54	C	0.38
S	0.40	0.49	SO ₂	0.68
Na	0.53	0.46	Na ₂ O	0.44
P	0.24	0.28	P ₂ O ₅	0.45
N	0.25	0.13	N	0.09

FOV: 839 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 15:48

LU-P1 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	34.70	38.34	SiO ₂	57.35
O	37.15	23.39		
Al	14.52	15.41	Al ₂ O ₃	20.36
Fe	4.61	10.12	Fe ₂ O ₃	10.12
K	1.44	2.22	K ₂ O	1.87
Ti	1.13	2.13	TiO ₂	2.49
Ag	0.33	1.40	Ag ₂ O	1.05
Y	0.40	1.39	Y ₂ O ₃	1.23
C	2.42	1.14	C	0.80
Nb	0.28	1.03	Nb ₂ O ₅	1.03
S	0.72	0.90	SO ₂	1.26
Cl	0.48	0.67	Cl	0.47
Ca	0.41	0.65	CaO	0.63
Mg	0.45	0.43	MgO	0.50
Na	0.33	0.30	Na ₂ O	0.28
N	0.45	0.25	N	0.17
P	0.19	0.23	P ₂ O ₅	0.37

FOV: 836 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 15:58

LU-P2 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	33.88	37.73	SiO ₂	56.84
O	34.26	21.73		
Al	10.32	11.04	Al ₂ O ₃	14.69
Fe	4.67	10.33	Fe ₂ O ₃	10.40
C	8.30	3.95	C	2.78
Nb	0.64	2.34	Nb ₂ O ₅	2.36
Ag	0.46	1.95	Ag ₂ O	1.47
K	1.18	1.83	K ₂ O	1.55
Y	0.49	1.73	Y ₂ O ₃	1.55
Ca	0.97	1.54	CaO	1.51
S	1.20	1.53	SO ₂	2.15
Ti	0.62	1.18	TiO ₂	1.39
Cl	0.65	0.91	Cl	0.64
P	0.57	0.70	P ₂ O ₅	1.13
Mg	0.72	0.70	MgO	0.81
Na	0.65	0.59	Na ₂ O	0.56
N	0.43	0.24	N	0.17

FOV: 839 μm, Mode: 15kV - Map, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 10:54

LU-P3 OX

Contains 1 image with a total of 1 analysis

Element Symbol	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.	Oxide Symbol	Stoichiometric wt Conc.
Si	31.41	33.46	SiO ₂	49.67
O	35.67	21.64		
Al	18.29	18.71	Al ₂ O ₃	24.54
Fe	2.34	4.95	Fe ₂ O ₃	4.91
Ti	2.13	3.86	TiO ₂	4.47
Ag	0.72	2.96	Ag ₂ O	2.21
K	1.92	2.85	K ₂ O	2.38
Y	0.81	2.74	Y ₂ O ₃	2.41
Nb	0.54	1.90	Nb ₂ O ₅	1.89
S	1.26	1.54	SO ₂	2.13
Cl	0.91	1.22	Cl	0.85
Ca	0.74	1.13	CaO	1.10
V	0.38	0.74	V ₂ O ₅	0.92
Mg	0.76	0.70	MgO	0.81
Na	0.62	0.54	Na ₂ O	0.51
P	0.46	0.54	P ₂ O ₅	0.86
C	0.56	0.25	C	0.18
N	0.48	0.25	N	0.18

FOV: 839 μm, Mode: 15kV - Point, Detector: BSD Full, Time: SEP 18 2020 15:19

APPENDIX 2

XRD TEST RESULTS

IRELEJARE SAMPLE

General information

Analysis date	2020-09-25 16:58:27	Measurement start time	2020-09-17 15:13:09
Analyst	Administrator	Operator	Administrator
Sample name	IRJ-P1	Comment	
Measured data name	C:\WallPaper\RESULTS\COALTAR\IRJ-P1_20200917_151141_G...	Memo	

Qualitative Analysis Results

Phase name	Formula	Figure of merit	Phase reg. detail	Space Group	DB Card Number
Kaolinite	Al ₂ Si ₂ O ₅ (O H) ₄	1.826	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	2 : P-1	00-001-0527
Clinochlore	Al - Fe - Si O ₂ - O H	3.199	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...		00-002-0022
Marialite	Na ₄ Al ₃ Si ₉ O ₂₄ Cl	3.297	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	87 : I4/m	00-002-0412
Illite	K Al ₂ Si ₃ Al O ₁₀ (O H) ₂	3.157	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	15 : C12/c1	00-002-0056
Quartz	Si O ₂	3.046	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	154 : P3221	01-070-7344
Sakhaite	H Ca ₁₂ Mg _{3.25} Fe _{0.75} Al _{0.2...}	3.272	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	227 : Fd-3m:2	04-011-7863

Plot of results

IRJ-P120200917_151141_G01_S01_M01

Table of results

Dataset / Weight Fraction,...	Value, Unit	Kaolinite	Clinochlore	Marialite	Illite	Quartz	Sakhaite
IRJ-P1_20200917_151141_...	0	14.5(12)	7.9(7)	0.2(6)	6.9(10)	54(2)	17(2)

GBELEJULODA SAMPLE

General information

Analysis date	2020-09-25 17:15:40	Measurement start time	2020-09-17 16:17:21
Analyst	Administrator	Operator	Administrator
Sample name	LODA-P1	Comment	
Measured data name	C:\WallPaper\RESULTS\COALTAR\LODA-P1_20200917_16013...	Memo	

Qualitative Analysis Results

Phase name	Formula	Figure of merit	Phase reg. detail	Space Group	DB Card Number
Kaolinite	Al ₂ Si ₂ O ₅ (O H) ₄	3.100	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	2 : P-1	00-001-0527
Clinochlore	Al - Fe - Si O ₂ - O H	3.412	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...		00-002-0022
Marialite	Na ₄ Al ₃ Si ₉ O ₂₄ Cl	3.206	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	87 : I4/m	00-002-0412
Illite	K Al ₂ Si ₃ Al O ₁₀ (O H) ₂	3.139	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	15 : C12/c1	00-002-0056
Quartz	Si O ₂	3.297	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	154 : P3221	01-070-7344
Sakhaite	H Ca ₁₂ Mg _{3.25} Fe _{0.75} Al _{0.2} ...	3.425	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	227 : Fd-3m:2	04-011-7863
Graphite	C	3.205	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	186 : P63mc	00-002-0456

Plot of results

LODA-P120200917_160137_G03_S03_M03

Table of results

Dataset / Weight Fracti...	Value, Unit	Kaolinite	Clinochlore	Marialite	Illite	Quartz	Sakhaite	Graphite
LODA-P1_20200917_16...	0	8.7(5)	0.64(11)	16(2)	18.9(12)	42.5(16)	8.1(5)	4.9(6)

TEMIDIRE SAMPLE

General information

Analysis date	2020-09-25 17:26:08	Measurement start time	2020-09-17 15:27:40
Analyst	Administrator	Operator	Administrator
Sample name	TM-P1	Comment	
Measured data name	C:\WallPaper\RESULTS\COALTAR\TM-P1_20200917_151141_...	Memo	

Qualitative Analysis Results

Phase name	Formula	Figure of merit	Phase reg. detail	Space Group	DB Card Number
Kaolinite	Al ₂ Si ₂ O ₅ (O H) ₄	3.190	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	2 : P-1	00-001-0527
Clinochlore	Al - Fe - Si O ₂ - O H	3.245	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...		00-002-0022
Marialite	Na ₄ Al ₃ Si ₉ O ₂₄ Cl	3.168	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	87 : I4/m	00-002-0412
Illite	K Al ₂ Si ₃ Al O ₁₀ (O H) ₂	3.409	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	15 : C12/c1	00-002-0056
Quartz	Si O ₂	3.217	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	154 : P3221	01-070-7344
Sakhaite	H Ca ₁₂ Mg _{3.25} Fe _{0.75} Al _{0.2} ...	2.995	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	227 : Fd-3m:2	04-011-7863

Plot of results

TM-P120200917_151141_G03_S03_M03

Table of results

Dataset / Weight Fraction,...	Value, Unit	Kaolinite	Clinocllore	Marialite	Illite	Quartz	Sakhaite
TM-P1_20200917_151141_...	0	21.9(19)	6.1(5)	0.6(9)	10(4)	61(3)	0.2(3)

ILUBIRIN SAMPLE

General information

Analysis date	2020-09-22 16:45:40	Measurement start time	2020-09-17 15:42:11
Analyst	Administrator	Operator	Administrator
Sample name	ILU-P1	Comment	
Measured data name	C:\WallPaper\RESULTS\COALTAR\ILU-P1_20200917_151141_...	Memo	

Qualitative Analysis Results

Phase name	Formula	Figure of merit	Phase reg. detail	Space Group	DB Card Number
Unnamed mineral (NR)	K Na ₃₁ Ca ₁₆ Al ₃₆ (Si O ₄) ₃ ...	0.949	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	143 : P3	04-015-1779
Quartz, syn	Si O ₂	0.999	S/M(PDF-4 Minerals 2020 R...	152 : P3121	01-086-1630
Marialite	Na ₄ Al ₃ Si ₉ O ₂₄ Cl	1.923	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	87 : I4/m	00-002-0412
Clinochlore	Al - Fe - Si O ₂ - O H	2.852	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...		00-002-0022
Illite	K Al ₂ Si ₃ Al O ₁₀ (O H) ₂	2.792	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	15 : C12/c1	00-002-0056
Kaolinite	Al ₂ Si ₂ O ₅ (O H) ₄	3.037	Import(PDF-4 Minerals 2020...	2 : P-1	00-001-0527

Plot of results

ILU-P120200917_151141_G05_S05_M05

Table of results

Dataset / Weight Fraction,...	Value, Unit	Unnamed mineral (N...	Quartz, syn	Marialite	Clinochlore	Illite	Kaolinite
ILU-P1_20200917_151141_...	0	11.2(7)	60(3)	13.6(17)	6.1(7)	5.2(3)	3.6(7)